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REVIEW ON SPEECH ANALYSIS UNDER DROWSINESS

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Abstract

Drowsiness is a major cause of accidents occurs in the area of Chemical Industry, Nuclear Power Plant, Air-ways, and Road-ways etc. This article reviews methods for measurement of drowsiness based on voice or speech analysis and also discusses concept of drowsiness and its effects on human life. It has been found that voice parameters change during transition into drowsiness. Therefore analysis of speech parameters during drowsiness may be promising variables for use in drowsy countermeasure devices. This review also identifies an operational approach to show the potential of voice as a robust indicator of human drowsiness. Although speech rate and fundamental frequency results mirrored the trends found by cognitive tests, there is scope for further analysis in a more controlled experimental environment with more sophisticated analysis procedures. With knowledge of the psychological (physiological) effects of drowsiness may lead to better drowsiness management.

Key Words: Drowsiness, Voice or Speech analysis, Cognitive tests, Psychological effects

1. Introduction

The purpose this review is to Measurement of drowsiness based on voice or speech analysis so 1st understand the occurrence of drowsiness and its impact on human life. Then measurement of drowsiness based on voice or speech analysis. As the speech data follow the same trend as the data from cognitive tests and subjective measures of alertness (H.P. Greeley, et.al. 2006 [1]). They also noted a strong circadian trend as the best voice performances occurring during normal waking hour and the worst performances occurring during normal sleeping hours.

Recently most safety-related research has focused on methods to reduce damage caused by transportation and air craft accidents while they are occurring or after these happen. Passive safety systems such as seat belts, airbags, and crashworthy body structures help to reduce the effects of an accident. In contrast the active safety system helps the drivers/pilots to avoid accidents by monitoring the state of the vehicle/air craft, the driver/pilot, or the surrounding traffic environment and providing alertness of driver/pilot or control interventions. Examples of active safety technologies include traction control systems, electronic stability control systems, forward collision warning and lane-departure warning systems, panic brake assist, lane-keeping aids, and automatic braking systems (Ji Hyun Yang, et.al., 2009 [2]). Those systems are monitor driver/pilot states such as where driver/pilot drowsiness also falls under the category of active safety systems (Ji Hyun Yang, et.al., 2009 [2]).

2. Drowsiness

Drowsiness is the intermediate state of alertness and sleep. It is a very critical state of human for those who perform some important task (like people who are working in chemical Industry, Nuclear Power Plant, process Industry, air-craft pilot, Driver etc.).

2.1. Factors of Drowsiness

Physiological and Environmental factors are two major factors causing drowsiness in case of humankind. Apart from these two, an Environmental factor plays a vital role for making drowsiness and those factors are: Stress, Noise, light, Excitement, Anger, and Pain etc. The drowsiness can be define in a better way that it can be classified into physical and mental categories (Saroj K.L. Lal et.al., 2001[3]).

2.1.1 Mental fatigue

Mental fatigue is gradual and cumulative process and associated with a disinclination for any effort, reduced efficiency and alertness and impaired mental performance. It should be understood that many factors could influence mental fatigue such as nutrition, physical health, environment, physical activity and recuperation periods. The major symptom of mental fatigue is a general sensation of weariness, feelings of inhibition and impaired activity. According to Saroj K.L. Lal et.al., in 2001[3] the states range from deep sleep, light sleep, drowsy, weary, hardly awake, relaxed, resting, fresh, alert, very alert, stimulated and a

state of alarm. In this context, mental fatigue is a functional state, which grades in one direction into sleep and in the other direction into a relaxed and restful condition, both of which are likely to reduce attention and alertness.

2.1.2 Physical fatigue

The phenomenon of reduced performance of a muscle after stress is called muscular fatigue and is characterized by reduced muscular power and movement. The chemical changes occur during muscular contraction to provide energy. Energy reserves in a stressed muscle (sugar and phosphorous) are depleted while lactic acid and carbon dioxide increase and the muscular tissue becomes acidic (Saroj K.L. Lal et.al., 2001[3]).

The Physical fatigue is a complex phenomenon influenced by numerous psycho physiological factors and has been linked with:

- a) A decline in alertness, mental concentration and motivation
- b) Reduced work output
- c) Weaker and slower muscular contractions
- d) Muscular tremor and localized pain
- e) Loading of respiratory, circulatory and neuromuscular functions
- f) A decrease in the frequency of the electromyogram (EMG) signal
- g) A decrease in duration of sustained isometric exertions and endurance time
- h) Increased lactate accumulation; and
- i) Increased core temperature (Basmajian and De Luca, 1985 and A. Strand and Rodahl, 1986).

Hard physical work before driving can also increase the risks of experiencing drowsiness during driving.

2.2 Effects of Drowsiness

Under drowsiness the brain gets stressed, memory gets hazier and dropping of concentration level so it affects our ability of thinking, stress handling capability, reduced problem solving capability, decision making capability etc.

So the typical effects of Drowsiness are

- a) Depression
- b) Heart disease
- c) Slurred speech
- d) Hyper tension
- e) Slower reaction times
- f) Reduced productivity or performance
- g) Reduced attention and vigilance
- h) Reduced decision making ability
- i) Reduced ability to do complex planning
- j) Reduced communication skills
- k) Reduced ability to manage stress and
- l) Loss of memory (Jarek Krajewski. et.al., 2009 [4] and S. K. Lal. et.al., 2001[3]).

3. Types of measurement

Drowsiness has an effect on various parts of the human body such as the brain, the cardiovascular system, the eyes, the vocal tract and vocal cord and based on this, various methods have been developed for detection of drowsiness. It is observed that the most accurate estimation of a subject's stress level is obtained by measuring physiological parameters (Lakshmi Swathi et.al., 2010 [5]).

In figure 1.1 (M. Hagmueller, et.al., 2006 [6]) describe the measurements may be taking blood tests or even insertion of electrodes into the brain; however many of these measurements are invasive types that comprise a kind of 'medical examination'. The Non-Invasive measurement techniques are that in which the body is not entered by puncture or incision. Still we can differentiate between measurements requiring physical contact such as a wrist-band sensor for measuring the heart-rate or electrodes applied on the skin for electroencephalogram (EEG) measurements and contact free measurements where no physical contact between the subject and the measuring device is necessary (M. Hagmueller, et.al., 2006 [6]).

Contact-Free measurements are favourable for drowsiness (stress) analysis in real-world situations since the application of sensors on a subject's body or inside the body can impair the subjects working capabilities or even be a cause of stress by itself. Under contact-free measures again define in two subgroups and differentiate between intrusive measures that interfere with the subject's privacy (such as a camera, video etc...) or the operator's job performance and non-intrusive measures, like, analysis of one's speech signal (M. Hagnmueller, et.al., 2006 [6]).

Fig 1.1 Types of Measurement

The Non-intrusive (voice/speech) is Nobel type of measurement for level of drowsiness.

4. Drowsiness effects on speech production

Under drowsiness both cognitive and physiological conditions are changes. Some consequences of drowsiness such as the decreased muscle tension or reduced body temperature can indirectly influence voice characteristics in the following stages of speech production (L.R. Rabiner, et.al., 2004 [7] and Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]):

- (a) Cognitive speech planning Respiration

- (b) Phonation
- (c) Articulation/resonance
- (d) Radiation (Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [8]).

These changes summarized in the cognitive-physiological mediator model (Fig 2 from J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]) are based on educated guesses. Nevertheless little empirical research has been done to examine these processes mediating between drowsiness and fatigue, speech production, and acoustic features. Drowsiness and fatigue has effect on the content and patterns of speech. Several indicators obtained from speech can be used for analyzing drowsiness. These include slurred speech, repetitive speech, slow or mumbled speech, flattened voice, decreased motivation and little high frequency energy. Flattened voice results less variation of pitch and hence, harmonic pattern becomes stable (J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]).

Furthermore, reduced muscle tone, resulting from the decreased motivation, may result in lowered pitch. Repetition of words or slow speech, changes the word duration. Many studies have shown in literature that many speech related features such as Pitch, Duration, Intensity, Glottal source properties and Vocal tract spectrum are considerably affected by drowsiness (Ji Hyun Yang, et.al., 2009 [2]).

Perhaps all of the variability of speech carries information about the state of the speaker. This is generally utilized in social interactions between humans; however the additional information is commonly not ‘understood’ by machines and human-machine interaction gets necessary there. In Harold P. Greeley, et.al., 2007 [9] they can use programs to this information from the speech and the variations in these ‘features’ can then be analyzed for the analysis of drowsiness and fatigue.

Furthermore a general decreased facial expression and thus decreased lip spreading (Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2008 [10]) may result in a shortening of the vocal tract and therefore in lower F1 and F2 formant frequencies. A supplemental factor for causing this effect can be seen in articulatory effects. The reduction of articulatorical effort leads to a smaller opening degree during slackened articulation and a decreasing of the first formant.

Fig. 2 Cognitive-physiological mediator model

Another sleepiness related voice phenomenon, which might have influence the formant values, is the shift of speech quality to a breathy, wide, lax, and non-tensed voice. The tensing of the vocal tract raises the larynx, which could result in an increased formant frequency. On the contrary a lax voice is characterised by low F1 (1st formant frequency) and wide F1 bandwidth. Similarly when the breathier a vowel is spoken then the wider is the first formant bandwidth (Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2008 [10]).

5. Acoustic Feature Computation

As non-intrusive measurement (i.e voice/speech) is a novel approach for detection of drowsiness. So this review paper describes a summary of approaches to the development of a voice-based drowsiness prediction system. Drowsiness causes changes in the articulation of voiced sounds and could be considered as representative of voice production mechanisms changes in the human body. i.e change in discrete voice parameters (such as fundamental frequency and word duration) has been reported in the literature, however, no single voice characteristic demonstrates a consistent and reliable change as the speakers become drowsy (H.P. Greeley, et.al., 2006 [11]).

The acoustic fatigue analysis is mainly based on speech emotion recognition research, general audio signal and computational intelligence research (Batliner et al., 2006). Acoustic features can be divided according to auditive-perceptual concepts in prosody (pitch, intensity, rhythm, pause pattern, and speech rate), articulation (slurred speech, reduction and elision phenomena), and speech quality (breathy, whispery, tense, sharp, hoarse, or modal voice). In 2009 J. Krajewski, et.al., [4] their approach prefers the fusion of purely signal processing based features without any known auditive-perceptual correlates and perceptual-acoustic features as the speech intensity (loudness), fundamental frequency (pitch), voiced/unvoiced duration (rhythm).

Typical acoustic features used in emotion speech recognition and audio processing are follows

- a) Fundamental frequency (acoustic equivalent to pitch; rate of vocal fold vibration; models prosodic structure and speech melody)
- b) Intensity (models volume and stressing structure)
- c) Linear predictive coding coefficients
- d) Harmonics-to-noise ratio (HNR; ratio between harmonic and aperiodic signal energy; breathiness and nasality indicator)
- e) Formant positions (resonance frequencies of the vocal tract depending strongly on lower jaw angle, tongue body angle, tongue body horizontal location, tongue tip angle, tongue tip horizontal location, relative lip height, lip protrusion, velum height)
- f) Formant bandwidths (model energy loss of speech signal due to vocal tract elasticity or heat conduction; yielding wall effect)
- g) Mel frequency cepstrum coefficients (MFCCs; separate filtering effects from the excitation signal in the time domain; entire speech production process reduced to a few decorrelated coefficients)
- h) Linear frequency cepstrum coefficients (LFCCs; emphasize changes or periodicity in the spectrum, while being relatively robust against noise)
- i) Duration of voiced/unvoiced speech segments (model temporal speech rhythm aspects as speech rate and pause structure) and

- j) Spectral features derived from the long term average spectrum (LTAS; relative amount of energy within predefined frequency bands; models speech quality as tense, rough and soft)(J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4] & Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [8]).

6. Detection of drowsiness using voice

Drowsiness does not depend on energy expenditure and it cannot be directly measured, but can be derived from visual and non-visual physiological features. Visual features mainly include posture, eye movement, head movement, and facial expression (Ji Hyun Yang, et.al. 2009 [2]). While Non-visual features mainly include heart rate variety depicted by ECG signals, and brain activity depicted by EEG signals (G. Yang, et.al., [12] and Lakshmi Swathi et.al., 2010 [5] but using the voice/speech parameter drowsiness can be detected [H.P. Greeley, et.al., 2006 [11] and T.L. New, et.al., 2006 [13].

In 1996 Whitmore et.al., [14] they considered the fundamental frequency and the duration of the voice as indicators of drowsiness. They observed that the fundamental frequency is consistent with the circadian pattern and the mean word pronunciation time decreases with the one stage to the other. In 1997 S. Milosevic, et.al., [15] considered intensity, pitch, duration, vocal tract spectrum, glottal source, and vocal tract articulator as parameters to indicate fatigue during an experiment on bus and truck drivers. He observed that the total sound pressure level of the sentence and its words were reduced two to three times after driving as compared to pre-driving conditions. Also, the duration of the phrase articulation after driving was somewhat prolonged. Krajewski et al. [4] computed high level contour descriptor features for assessing fatigue during a simulated driving experiment with sleep deprivation. They also validated the approach using Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS). In 2009 K. Shiomi, et.al., [16] they calculate the Lyapunov exponents from the human voices strange attractor which are used to measure fatigue and observed that it increase before the subjects start to feel fatigued or sleepy.

The expressiveness of the acoustic parameters has a direct impact on analysing the effect of drowsiness on speech so short-time spectral coefficients that capture the variations of pitch and harmonic pattern to analyse speech parameters. Several experiments are conducted to

evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed features. In 2006 T.L. New et.al., they conduct an experiment by using continuous density HMM (Hidden Markov Model) with four states and two Gaussian mixtures per state for all HMM models. Using training database they train the two HMM models for Normal Speech (NS) and Sleep Deprived Speech (SDS), Duration dialogues and Response time. If their speech segments are longer than 2 seconds, the speech is segmented into 1 second segments. The classification decision is made on the test segments of one second or less than one second. They conduct the experiment to compare the system performance of three feature types, namely, PHSC (pitch & harmonic frequency spectral coefficients), MFCC and LPCC. They explain that PHSC feature can perform well to represent difference in speech characteristics between NS and SDS. In PHSC, two-layer cascaded sub band filters captures information of pitch and harmonic variations of SDS and NS, and integrate this information into spectral coefficients (T.L. New, et.al., 2006 [13]).

According to T.L. New, et.al., 2006 [13] in addition to the short-time spectral coefficients, they use duration information to analyse speech parameters. The need for micro sleep and lapses increases when sleep deprivation progresses. As a result the ability to perform the work as well as motivation is reduced (H.P. Greeley, et.al., 2006 [11]). This can be measured by Response-Time (RT) which is a measure of how fast Follower responds to the Giver's instruction. RT is the duration between ending point of the Giver's instruction and starting point of the Follower's response. Starting points of utterances for both Givers and Followers within the dialogues are provided in the database. Ending points of the utterances are obtained by using some simple energy threshold method. Cepstral analysis results in the calculation of a discrete number of coefficients called cepstral coefficients. With this analysis, the entire human speech production process can be described by only a few cepstral coefficients. Instead of tracking changes in specific vocal metrics, such as formants, one can use these cepstral coefficients. These cepstral coefficients constitute the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC). The MFCC feature vector can be used for drowsiness analysis. The feature vector is comprised cepstral coefficients, along with their first and second time derivatives. Also of interest is that the MFCC vector changes as a function of the subject's level of fatigue or drowsiness (H.P. Greeley, et.al., 2006 [11]).

In 2006 H.P. Greeley, et.al., [11] they determine the MFCC vectors for specific phones from the fatigue prediction software relies on ASR. It is critical that the correct phones are identified from the input stream of audio data. Eight mixture Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) were used to represent the statistics of the training data. A loop grammar was used as a language model due to the small vocabulary size. The output of the ASR system was one-best phone alignments with the word likelihood score annotated to each phone hypothesis. The main interest is in finding the presence of certain phones with a high degree of confidence for detection of drowsiness. Annotating the one-best hypothesis with confidence measures would help in reducing false hypothesis. A threshold can be used to filter less probable words in the final hypothesis. Word posteriors computed from word graphs were used as a confidence estimate.

MFCC's are the most common parameterization schemes employed in current recognition tasks. MFCC parameters are obtained in the frequency domain with critical band windowing of the speech spectrum (Ruhi Sarikaya et.al., 2000[17]). These MFCC components are change if the subjects get increasingly drowsy (H.P. Greeley, et.al., 2006 [11]). In 2010 According to Lakshmi Swathi et.al., the Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC) has been used as feature in a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) based classifier to segregate voiced, unvoiced and silence parts of the speech. They have used short time analysis of speech since the acoustic properties of the speech changes continuously during an utterance. For this, they first divide the sample into frames. Normally for most phonemes the properties of the speech remain invariant for a short period of time (~5-100 ms). This segmentation is not error free since it creates blocking effects that makes a rough transition in the representation of two consecutive frames. Hence they have applied Hamming window to each data frame. Windowing is also required to mitigate the effects of spectral leakage. This windowed signal is transformed into frequency domain via the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and the magnitude spectrum is passed through a bank of triangular shaped filters whose center frequencies are spaced along the perceptually motivated Mel-frequency scale (S. Ramamohan et.al., 2006 [18]. The energy output from each filter is then log-compressed and transformed into Cepstral domain via the DCT to obtain the MFCC (Ruhi Sarikaya et.al., 2000 [17]. MFCC is a representation of a short term power spectrum of sound based on a cosine transform of a log power spectrum on a non-linear Mel scale of frequency. The Mel

scale is a perceptually motivated scale of pitches judged by listeners to be equal in distance from one another. The reference point between this scale and normal frequency measurement is defined by equating a 1000 Hz tone, which is 40 dB above the listener's threshold, with a pitch of 1000 Mels. In the resulting scale, 1 Mel represents one-thousandth of the pitch of 1 kHz and an increase of Mels by a factor 2 causes the pitch to double. The relation between frequency hertz and Mel frequency (m) is given in equation (1) (T F. Quatieri, 2007[19]).

$$m = 1127.01048 \times \log\left(\frac{f}{700} + 1\right) \text{ mels} \text{ ----- (1)}$$

In 2010 Lakshmi Swathi et.al., 2010 [5] they estimated the phonetic information by using several Gaussian distributed functions and to classify between voiced and unvoiced parts of speech by using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) classifier.

Acoustic features can be divided according to auditive-perceptual concepts in prosody (pitch, intensity, rhythm, pause pattern, and speech rate), articulation (slurred speech, reduction and elision phenomena), and speech quality (breathy, tense, sharp, hoarse, or modal voice). Another distinction can be drawn from using signal-processing categories such as time domain, frequency domain, or state space features (Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [8]). In 2009 J. Krajewski, et.al., [4] they estimated the 59 frame-level based descriptor (FLD) contours: fundamental frequency, fundamental frequency peak process, intensity, HNR, formant position and bandwidth (F1-F6), 15 LPCs, 12 MFCCs, 12 LFCCs, 1 LFCC-flux (Euclidean distance of two consecutive LFCC frame vectors), duration of voiced, duration of unvoiced speech segments, and long term average spectrum (LTAS) (J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]) and for the purpose of feature selection they have used a relevance maximizing then redundancy minimizing correlation filter approach. To enhance robustness of the classification they feed these features separately into 8 sophisticated standard machine learning methods (multilayer perceptron (MLP), support vector machine linear kernel (SVM_l) and radial kernel (SVM_r), 5-nearest neighbour (5-NN), decision tree (DT), Parzen classifier (PC), logistic regression (LR), and linear discriminant analysis (LDA). By averaging the classification outputs, an ensemble classifier was created (J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]).

In 2009 Jarek Krajewski, et.al., [8] their approach prefers the fusion of perceptual features with purely signal-processing and speech-recognition-based features, without any known

auditive-perceptual pendants. Typical frame-level-based acoustic features used in emotion speech recognition and audio processing are fundamental frequency, energy, harmonics-to-noise ratio (HNR), formant position and bandwidth ($F1-F6$), MFCCs, linear frequency cepstrum coefficients (LFCCs), duration of voiced/unvoiced speech segments, and spectral features derived from the long-term average spectrum (LTAS), such as band-energies, roll-off, centroid or spectral flux (Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2009[8] & J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]).

6.1. Drowsiness prediction for drivers

When drivers were sleep-deprived then their performance of responding to unexpected disturbances degraded, while they were robust enough to continue the routine driving tasks such as lane tracking, vehicle following and lane changing (Ji Hyun Yang, et.al., 2009 [2]). In 1997 S. Milosevic et.al., [15] represent a possible approach to study of driver fatigue by questionnaire investigation. Generally questionnaire studies provide information about signs of fatigue, time of fatigue appearance, and other factors that solely or partially contribute to the driver's fatigue. Like stimulus-response tasks were given to each subject in a random order during the driving. Stimulus can be an auditory ringing signal, a visual symbol, or a lane-change sign on the driving lane (Ji Hyun Yang, et.al., 2009 [2]). Alertness was quantified by assessing brain activity and blinking. Their device detects the steering wheel patterns associated with drowsiness and emits a warning to the driver. The above studies provide some convincing examples of the feasibility of using neurophysiologic measures to create an automated system to track and compensate for lapses in the alertness of human operators with EEG appearing to be the most promising (S. K. Lal. et.al., 2001[3]).

6.2. Drowsiness prediction for Pilots

Drowsiness is a very real problem especially on long-haul flights crossing many time zones. If an increase in the probability of crew micro-sleep and/or human error could be detected, it might be possible to warn the pilot so that he may be relieved by other on-board crew members. Such a monitoring system could be installed as airborne equipment if it were made sufficiently compact. To measure the fatigue and the probability of occurrence of drowse of a

human subject in real-time by voice analysis. The strange attractor of the human voice changes over time. It is thought by Kakuichi Shiomi in 2009 that the human voice strange attractor's Liapunov exponents indicate the mental and physical condition (i.e. fatigue or drowsy) of a subject. They develop a predictor which can estimate fatigue and probability of occurrence of drowse from voice. This predictor has been developed on a personal computer as an application of digital signal processing based on the theory of Chaos, and is designed to work in real-time. This predictor is able to predict micro-sleep and drowse of pilots and air traffic controllers from their verbal communications (K. Shiomi, et.al., 2009 [16]).

7. Future work on detection of Drowsiness

There are still a number of limitations to the researchers presented here. The major criticism refers to the choice of the applied ground truth. Until now, many studies found associations between physiological data (e.g. eye blink duration) and fatigue. Nevertheless, they offer difficulties because of large inter-individual variability. This forecloses the development of commonly accepted scaling as it is realized e.g. with the KSS (J. Krajewski, et.al., 2009 [4]).

The review approach to voice analysis is unique in that it does not focus on a single, discrete, voice parameter but, instead, examines changes in a mathematical representation of the entire voice (the cepstral components). This representation is highly individual-specific; in fact, this part is in how voice recognizers work. The sensitivity and specificity of this voice-based approach should be determined by way of testing similar to that reported with an analysis of individual voice data from a significantly larger population of subjects. The resulting drowsiness estimation system should serve as a decision aid tool. However, due to variable sensitivity and specificity typical of most biomedical measurements the final determination of fatigue-related effects should still be the task of a human evaluator (Harold P. Greeley, et.al., 2007 [9]). It would seem advisable that future studies address the main topics of improving the acoustic sleepiness analysis and finding evidence for its validity in real-world applications.

There are some limitations of this study that sleepiness might be confounded by annoyance states due to the multiple repetition of speak task. And many results are limited by the facts

that they did not consider real life speaking conditions including variation in speakers' states (having a head cold, drinking milk, being nervous, aggressive or in a depressive mood), variations in speakers' trait (strong dialect, older age), and variations in situational context factors (high driving related work-load situation, noisy environments). Furthermore the analysis assumes a closely placed microphone and noise-free recordings of short sentences. However, it is not realistic to expect such a clean audio input, especially not in unconstrained traffic environments in which automatic sleepiness detection systems are most likely to be deployed.

Future studies need to address the following topics:

- a) Temporal segmentation: finding sleepiness sensitive phonetic units (vowels or consonant cluster in different positions within words and phrasal units)
- b) feature extraction: computing time-domain based features from nonlinear time series analysis (lyapunov exponents, correlation dimension, auto mutual information, time resolved density, fractal dimensions, multi scale entropies and recurrence quantification analysis); using automatic feature generation
- c) Pattern classification: dividing between male and female classification models; utilizing SVMs, maximum likelihood bayes classifiers, kNNs, fuzzy membership indexing, ANNs, HMMs, Gaussian mixture density models; using sophisticated ensemble classification methods (J. Krajewski, et.al., 2007 [20]).
- d) Different validation designs: following the circadian sleepiness cycle, pharmacological studies, randomized controlled trials (between-subject designs) (Jarek Krajewski, et.al., 2009[8]).

It would seem advisable that future studies address the main topics of improving the acoustic sleepiness analysis and finding evidence for its validity in real-world applications.

8. Conclusion

This review study took an operational approach to show the potential of voice as a robust indicator of human fatigue. Although speech rate and fundamental frequency results mirrored those found on the cognitive tests, further discoveries may be made in a more controlled

experimental environment with more sophisticated analysis procedures. Use of a test phrase which has greater contextual relevance may result in greater differences over time in fundamental frequency and speech rate. In addition, complete sleep deprivation over a long period would probably result in greater levels of subjective fatigue and greater variations in vocal properties. Relatively advanced analysis procedures like shimmer and jitter would also delve into the finer striations of speech quality and may well turn up some variation overlooked by the gross measures used in this study. Further research is required given the evidence for speech properties to change over a sustained wakefulness period. The results of this investigation can be used to conclude that voice may be useful in describing the fatigue state of the speaker. Both vocal measurements were found to vary as would be expected given normal circadian variation in humans.

This review indicates that fatigue is a prevalent and potentially dangerous transport related condition. Therefore, fatigue countermeasures are needed that could provide an important solution to fatigue related accidents. From the review of the literature and our recent study on voice appears to be a promising indicator of driver fatigue. The main voice characteristics are changes during drowsiness. Therefore a valid measure of drowsiness such as the pitch, MFCC, LPC, LFCC, etc. seems to promising for the development of a drowsiness countermeasure device. Furthermore the stimulus delivered when the performance impairment due to fatigue is detected must successfully restore normal performance. In the future, such an enabling technology could be important in the transport, aviation, military and industrial environments that demand alertness and that involve multiple tasks competing for limited attention resources. An independent validation criterion for drowsiness should be utilized such as video monitoring of changes in facial features to provide an objective indicator of drowsiness. Furthermore, to date there have been no studies to identify whether the psycho physiological changes during fatigue are reproducible on different days.

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